

Supplementary material and data associated to the manuscript

**SEASONAL VARIATIONS IN FEMORAL GLAND SECRETIONS
REVEALS SOME UNEXPECTED CORRELATIONS BETWEEN
PROTEIN AND LIPID COMPONENTS IN A LACERTID LIZARD**

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Here we present the link (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2556554>) to a zip file where all the data, R scripts and functions used in the article have been stored. After downloading and unzipping it in a working directory, you will be able to reproduce all the analyses. Of course, you need R (with the required packages), and JAGS already installed on your computer.

The material is organized in three folders, while the scripts and the readme file are in the root.

- “gel” = folder where all the original SDS-PAGE gel images are stored
- “data” = folder where all the data (both input and output) are stored
- “functions” = folder where the *ad hoc* functions are available as “.R” files (text files)

The three scripts are ordered from the gel acquisition procedure (01) to the cosinor model analysis (03). Since some steps could take a lot of computational time, the intermediate results are already available as “.Rdata” file in the data folder. Scripts are commented and you should be able to follow the procedure, as well to start from any intermediate point. A “season.csv” file with the complete dataset has been also made available for those who are interested in looking at the raw data.